

moderately resistant to B1 and ShB, and moderately susceptible to BB.

NC493 (IET8989), released as Amulya, is a selection from the land race Najani. It is photoperiod-sensitive and flowers 26-28 Oct. Panicles are long, compact, and well-exserted, with more than 200 long slender grains (6.4 mm

long, 3.1 L/B ratio); 1,000-grain weight is 24 g. Highest yield was 7.4 t/ha in uniform variety trials at Arundhutinagar, Tripura, in 1985. Amulya is resistant to ShB and moderately resistant to BB and SB.

CN570-652-39-2 (IET10001), released as Dinesh, is from a cross

between Jaladhi 2 and Pankaj. It flowers 30 Oct-3 Nov. It has good kneeing ability. Panicles are 22 cm long with 185 short bold grains (5.9 mm long, 2.0 L/B ratio). It had the highest yield (4.8 t/ha) at Chinsurah in 1987. It is moderately resistant to ShB and B1 and moderately susceptible to BB. ■

Seed technology

Hand-operated vacuum packing system for rice seed storage

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We developed a hand-operated vacuum packing system to facilitate dry seed storage. Reducing the oxygen content in sealed containers prevents seed rehydration and suffocates, adult insects. Components of the vacuum packing system are

- a bicycle tire pump, with pump plunger seal or cup in reverse, to use as the vacuum pump;
- a tire inner tube stem valve, to use as a check valve to prevent backflow of air into the vacuum chamber;
- a large food can, irrigation pipe, or pressure cooker to use as the vacuum chamber;

- a lid for the vacuum chamber, used with a rubber gasket made from a tire inner tube and sheet metal or wood;
- a glass jar with a screw cap and gasket or a lid with a plastic inner liner, to use as the storage container.

Seeds are placed in the glass jar and its lid is twisted on snugly, but not so tight that air cannot escape during evacuation. The jar is placed in the vacuum chamber, the chamber evacuated, and the vacuum released rapidly. The rapid intake of air into the vacuum chamber will slam the jar lid down and seal it. Tightening the screw cap will help secure the seal.

A vacuum system using a 16-cm-diameter × 17-cm-high food can requires 8-15 strokes with the modified (4-cm-diameter × 62-cm-high) bicycle pump to attain a vacuum adequate for sealing. We have easily achieved 50-80 kPa

Vacuum packing system: a) bicycle pump with reversed cup, b) tire stem valve, c) rubber stopper, d) sheet metal or plywood, e) rubber gasket, f) jar, and g) food can.

(15-25 inches mercury) suction. Larger vacuum chambers need more strokes to achieve the desired air evacuation.

Including dehydrating agents, such as silica gel, in the storage jar facilitates moisture control. ■

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Physiology and plant nutrition

Rice mitochondria surface membrane contains concanavalin A receptors

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Cell organoids membranes contain the residues of different sugars. The residues in surface membranes provide informational cooperation with other organoids, transport molecules, etc. The presence of sugar residue in the surface membrane of

1. Rice mitochondria stained with Con A gold conjugate suspension.

2. Rice mitochondria stained with Con A gold conjugate.